

How the Corruption of Grassroots Cadres Deprives People's Happiness

Jun Han¹

Abstract

Grassroots cadres are managers responsible for grassroots governance and serve as the final interpreters and executors of central government policies. They play a critical role in policy implementation, particularly in the "last mile" of the process. However, despite the government's efforts to implement public policies, corruption among grassroots cadres in the field of people's livelihoods is on the rise, and the severity of exposed corruption is increasing. This study is based on a survey of people's livelihoods in northern Jiangsu, China. Firstly, it summarizes the corruption phenomenon observed in the survey, which mainly focuses on the significant corruption problems faced by grassroots leaders, the expanding fields of corruption, and the complicated and changeable methods used. Secondly, based on on-the-spot investigations, the study finds that the frequent corruption among grassroots leaders is due to obstacles that hinder efforts to promote corruption management at the village level. Finally, based on the study's conclusions, policy recommendations are made to prevent the corruption of grassroots cadres.

Keywords

corruption; happiness deprivation; grassroots governance; grassroots cadres; China

¹ Jun Han (ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7615-7333>) is a research assistant at the High-Quality Development Evaluation Institute at the Nanjing University of Posts and Telecommunications, Nanjing, China. Email: njhanjun@njupt.edu.cn.

Introduction

Corruption has been a pervasive phenomenon in human politics, arising from the inherent self-serving nature of humans and the social power inherent in public institutions within a particular political milieu or social context. While corruption represents a significant social and political challenge, attributed to the inherent nature of humans, its complete eradication is impossible due to the limited rationality inherent in human existence. As a result, a comprehensive and ongoing process of scrutiny is required in order to effectively address and evaluate major corruption cases. Moreover, the prevalence of corruption serves as an objective criterion for evaluating a nation's political civilization, historical and social advancement.

Throughout history, corruption has been a pervasive social phenomenon, intimately connected to the transfer of state power, both past and present, and manifested in various forms across societies. Currently, corruption is ranked fourth among the world's most pressing public hazards, following terrorism, AIDS, and drugs, and it presents a formidable challenge to all nations. Nevertheless, corrupt practices at the grassroots level remain prominent in most countries, despite the heightened anti-corruption measures implemented by many governments. Many public officials at the local level continue to exploit loopholes in laws and regulations, taking advantage of the perceived gap between the right to use public resources honestly and the right to flout the law, which constitutes corruption.

Although the incidence of corruption at the grassroots level may be low-key and often tolerated by the masses, its negative impact on society cannot be disregarded. This type of corruption diminishes the government's efficiency, undermines its credibility, fosters a culture of corruption, and eventually threatens the foundation of the political system if allowed to persist unchecked. Therefore, it is imperative to effectively curb corruption among civil servants at the grassroots level.

The purpose of this paper is to investigate the field operations of five prefecture-level cities in the Northern part of the Jiangsu (江苏省) region in China: Xuzhou (徐州市), Lianyungang (连云港市), Suqian (宿迁市), Huai'an (淮安市), and Yancheng (盐城市). The study covers 17 municipal districts and 3 county-level cities that represent a range of community types, including street-subordinate communities, township-subordinate communities, county-level cities' streets, and rural areas. The study focuses on several issues, including conducting interviews with units responsible for people's livelihood projects to obtain a comprehensive understanding of their operation and management practices.

Additionally, the study involves home visits to individuals aged 18-59 years, people over 60, and beneficiaries of people's livelihood projects to capture their feedback on the effectiveness of the projects. Furthermore, the study includes on-site observations and personal experiences of the local social and economic development, as well as evaluations of grassroots cadres. Lastly, the study analyzes nearly 10,000 pieces of dynamic data and interview materials at the district, county, street, and village levels to gain a better understanding of the subject matter.

Our comprehensive investigation revealed that grassroots managers play a crucial role in implementing decisions made by higher authorities, while village-level cadres, i.e., village committee members, act as intermediaries between the government and the masses. Their responsibilities include implementing policies, representing the party and government, and addressing people's interests and grievances directly. Despite years of anti-corruption efforts, corruption persists at the grassroots level due to political, economic, ideological, and external factors. Some officials have been coerced by religious groups or criminal organizations, while others have colluded with these groups to engage in corrupt activities.

Literature review

Heidenheimer (1989) proposed the "three-color corruption theory" as a framework to explore public acceptance of corruption. In his theory he used three different shades, white, gray, and black, as reference points to distinguish between different forms of corruption. White corruption, being the most tolerable type, is often unnoticed and has fewer detrimental effects on society. Consequently, punishing this form of corruption usually leads to negative reactions (Duerrenberger & Warning, 2018). Gray corruption is more difficult to tolerate than white corruption, but it is still less harmful, and some individuals are averse to it while others remain indifferent. Black corruption, on the other hand, is the most severe form of corruption, and it is unacceptable to most members of society. It challenges both the legal and moral boundaries of society to varying degrees. The classification proposed by Heidenheimer helps to understand the attitudes, perceptions, and social impacts of all social strata towards corruption.

Baez-Camargo et al. (2020) argue that there is a grey area between "black corruption" and "white corruption," making it difficult to define and contain, resulting in varied attitudes and reactions from individuals. Haass and Ottmann (2017) suggest that black corruption includes a series of publicly condemned behaviors that are illegal or criminal, such as abuse of power for personal gain (Montes & Paschoal, 2016), bribery (Serritzlew et al., 2014), and power abuse for extortion (Jetter & Parmeter, 2018). In contrast, white corruption is less severe than black corruption, yet still involves impure behaviors or situations, such as reciprocal corruption (Fjelde & De Soysa, 2009). Currently, the public exhibits high tolerance and acceptance of "white corruption." Gray corruption, according to Chowdhury (2004), exists in a gray area between right and wrong, and it is neither entirely guilty nor innocent. It mainly comprises business transactions, collusion between government and enterprises, and wasteful spending by government units. Due to the complex relationships and economic exchanges involved, gray corruption is often overlooked by the public despite being highly harmful and widespread.

The paper by Agbo and Iwundu (2016) examines corruption and identifies two types: big corruption and micro-corruption. Big corruption involves illegal procedures, while micro-corruption, also known as sub-corruption, pertains to personal thoughts and behaviors that harm the interests of the masses (Gong & Ren, 2013). Effective governance measures must be taken based on the type and degree of corruption. Heywood and Rose (2017) describe micro-corruption as the behavior of grassroots cadres who use their power to seek personal gain for themselves or others and harm the interests of the masses. According to Neudorfer (2018), micro-corruption is not explicitly illegal and does not necessarily entail legal responsibility, often exploiting loopholes in laws and policies by cadres to gain personal benefits. Hydén (2014) argues that corruption among grassroots power is prevalent, often occurring at the edge of laws or policies, and within the scope of clean-up. Pellegrini (2011) describe micro-corruption as hidden, far-reaching, and outside the scope of legal punishment. Zaloznaya (2014) identifies the features of grassroots power corruption, including abundant opportunities, humanization, and low difficulty. Perumal (2021) attributes the source of grassroots power corruption to interpersonal communication and reciprocity, which can confuse people and make them fail to recognize the harm. Finally, Dong and Torgler (2014) analyze grassroots corruption from the perspective of state-owned enterprises and find that middle-level and bottom-level party member cadres are particularly vulnerable to corrupt practices.

The academic community has widely examined the causes of corruption in grassroots power from two perspectives: government governance and public officials' self-restraint. Lindberg and Orjuela (2014) suggest that corruption thrives in the political culture of grassroots society, in which

notions such as the clan concept and official standards create an environment for corruption to flourish. At the grassroots level, "small groups" and "small circles" often influence cadres, who possess a sense of privilege and are impacted by the dual political and resource allocation pattern, leading to "micro-corruption." Factors such as low morality among cadres, inactive work, and incorrect views contribute to corruption in grassroots power, as argued by Benfratello et al. (2017). Fisman and Gatti (2002) contend that controlling grassroots corruption is difficult due to failures in law, supervision, and the system. Hegre and Nygård (2015) employ the politics of transaction costs, proposing that the inducement of "micro-corruption" is due to the political transaction costs caused by unsmooth information, opportunism, and asset specificity.

The grassroots power governance model

The current Chinese society is marked by a highly mobile rural population and an increasingly complex governance pattern, which have become prominent features. These features also constitute the external environment that grassroots governance is presently facing. Therefore, grassroots organizations must adjust to these changes.

The space of grassroots administrative power. Since China's reform and opening up, the government has gradually established a governance model that includes township and village governments in rural areas. The township government is responsible for exercising state functions and providing services to develop villages, while village-level organizations focus on ensuring villagers' autonomy and exercising self-governance over local affairs. This model is supposed to create a relatively balanced and interdependent relationship between state power and village autonomy, which allows for relatively autonomous village governance (Gong & Ren, 2013).

However, as the state leads the modernization process and adjusts its policies on grassroots governance, the administrative power of the township government has come to dominate the construction of rural social governance order (Dong & Torgler, 2013). While this ensures the state's social integration and political control over rural society, it has also reduced the autonomous space for grassroots governance due to the one-way expansion of administrative power (Goldberg, 2018; Murphy & Yetmar, 2019). The spatial scope of grassroots administrative power can be explained by considering the following two aspects.

The strengthening of grassroots administrative power has resulted in the township governments' enhanced supervision and control functions. Since the beginning of the 21st century, China's villages and towns have implemented the combination of villages and groups. This has abolished the village group leader and established the administrative village as the basic unit of village-level governance. Some regions have also explored the possibility of strengthening the downward extension of grassroots power by setting up an informal district system between villages and towns (Zaloznaya, 2014). In the rural governance process, the district leaders promote all work in villages and towns, and also handle all affairs and demands from the masses. By adjusting the governance level, the unit of village-level governance moves up, and the district becomes a powerful tentacle for the extension of grassroots power downward and the starting point for the infiltration and control of local state power (Cooray et al., 2017).

However, while the appointment of district leaders has increased the flexibility of grassroots government work, the township government has achieved all-round supervision of villages through district leaders, resulting in more qualitative and powerful transmission of administrative pressure between villages (McQueen, 2016; Themudo, 2012). As a result, the autonomy space of village-level governance is gradually shrinking, and village-level governance is largely restricted by higher executive

power. This is partly due to the country's system adjustment and the development level of various regions. Therefore, the governance level serves as the spatial carrier of the national governance structure, reflecting not only the vertical relationship of governance units, but also highlighting the power allocation and interest relationship between the central and the local government (Méndez & Sepúlveda, 2006). As administrative power continues to intervene, the township government's control over village-level organizations strengthens, resulting in problems with administering village governance and weakening governance capability.

The management system of grassroots organizations. The Chinese central government has implemented administrative reforms at the grassroots level, in response to various economic and social developments and to governance modernization. As a result, village-level organizations have been restructured according to a formal administrative hierarchy, creating a hierarchical, professional management style. This has led to the formation of a "two committees" cadre management pattern, where the secretary and the director work in tandem. Village-level governance has emerged as a relatively independent field, with more complex objectives, challenging tasks, and specific governance forms.

In rural societies, however, certain jobs are difficult to carry out with a professional division of labor, due to their complexity, which requires coordination and cooperation across departments. These jobs are usually project-based, with emphasis on overall planning, flexibility, and can't be accomplished solely by cadres of a particular department. Additionally, verification and collection of specific information require high levels of accuracy and familiarity with the local people and the local context in the village, as well as constant mobilization of villagers. This highly dispersed and irregular rural society needs a more flexible and efficient organizational form. While clear division of labor and complete organization can lead to the effective operation of the entire bureaucracy system, it is challenging to match the flexibility, integration, and integrity of a rural society. The primary issue is that the professional division of labor of village cadres is difficult to adapt to the irregularity of rural society.

The complexity of grassroots governance has increased the need for specialized personnel and has reinforced the importance of a professional division of labor. To ensure effective communication with higher-level functional departments, a significant amount of administrative technical knowledge and information management has been integrated into rural governance. This requires grassroots managers to possess professional skills and meet certain work standards. The significance of personnel quality in rural governance has become, thus, more prominent, underscoring the indispensability of governance subjects. This, in turn, limits the scope of cooperation between grassroots managers and increases the difficulty of collaboration. For instance, rural financial work involves a set of rigorous procedural systems for management and approval, which cannot be efficiently handled by general grassroots managers. The absence of financial managers at the grassroots level can lead to suspension of rural accounting.

Grassroots administrative affairs. Grassroots administrative organizations play a crucial role in the self-management and self-service of villagers and serve as a platform for village governance to address the endogenous needs of rural society. However, in rural governance, village-level organizations have transformed into departments that serve the higher-level government, with grassroots managers acting as executors of governance tasks and becoming more aligned with the will of the higher-level government. As a result, administrative affairs at the grassroots level have become highly concentrated, consuming most of the energy of grassroots managers.

Before the agricultural tax reform in China, grassroots administrative management was primarily concerned with tax collection and family planning. After the reform, the government's role shifted from "governance" to "service," and the task of grassroots administrative governance also changed. With the introduction of policies to benefit farmers and the construction of a service-oriented government in the State Council, a significant number of administrative and governance tasks are now delegated to the grassroots level. This has led to an increase in the workload of routine services, which mainly involve grassroots managers working closely with farmers on matters such as family planning, civil affairs for disabled persons, labor security, and agricultural services. As a result, more functional departments are delegating administrative services to rural grassroots managers to promote the expansion of services and policies to the grassroots level. This, in turn, has resulted in grassroots management organizations becoming administrative units that are extended downward by higher government departments, thereby increasing the burden on grassroots administrative organizations.

Moreover, procedural administrative services have increased, requiring grassroots managers to handle a large number of documents and statements that require a certain level of cultural and information operation ability. This has significantly increased the workload of grassroots managers, limiting their time and energy to address other tasks. In addition, the center's working pressure has increased, with township governments dispatching administrative tasks to each administrative village through central work, realizing the infiltration and transformation of administrative will through target locking, task decomposition, index quantification, process supervision, and result examination. Under this pressure system, village-level organizations have limited space to make their own choices, and the power of village cadres to deal with affairs comes from administrative pressure.

To better implement state policies and regulate the behavior of grassroots managers and village cadres, transaction governance in village-level affairs is becoming increasingly formalized. Formalization is mainly manifested in two aspects: the procedural process and the formal content (Gong & Ren, 2013). The modernization of grassroots governance has resulted in a gradual shift towards standardization and normalization in village-level governance (Oto-Peralías et al., 2013). The focus of grassroots governance has also evolved from prioritizing only the completion of results to prioritizing the legalization of processes. This emphasis on "procedural justice" has become an important requirement of village-level governance in the new era. However, the pursuit of procedural justice not only increases administrative costs, but also substitutes the outcome of governance with the process, overlooking the differentiated needs of different villages and the complexities of governance. For instance, collective funds are managed differently now, with a focus on meeting system requirements rather than maximizing their utility.

The status quo of power corruption at the grassroots level

Since the 18th National Congress of the Communist Party of China, the central government has launched various anti-corruption efforts, and grassroots measures have yielded practical results. A "report card" issued by the Central Commission for Discipline Inspection and the Ministry of Supervision revealed that over 10,000 township-level cadres were disciplined for work-style violations in the past five years. However, the vast number of party organizations at all levels in China presents significant challenges to the effectiveness of anti-corruption efforts. As such, there are still several deficiencies in grassroots measures, including the following aspects.

Grassroots corruption forms emerge in endlessly, and "hidden" corruption increases. The increased anti-corruption efforts at both central and local levels have had a positive impact on raising

awareness among most party members. However, despite these efforts, some individuals remain oblivious to the root causes of their corrupt practices, leading to a situation where policies at the top are often circumvented. Certain individuals abuse their power and use underhanded tactics to perpetuate corruption, taking advantage of policy loopholes. Although the acceptance of gifts and public bribery has decreased in many regions, new forms of corruption have emerged, such as the misuse of public funds for personal entertainment and corruption concerning matters related to the welfare of citizens, which can leave rural residents with unfulfilled needs. The appointment and election of officials at the grassroots level often involves cronyism and re-election of officials for extended periods, leading to the entrenchment of power and interests. These corrupt practices have an adverse impact on the quality of life of the people and their basic rights and interests, leading to reduced funding for social welfare programs and other areas.

The "clique" is in vogue. The countryside serves as a place where clan consciousness and personal relationships are reinforced. However, the traditional mindset of small-scale peasants may lead to the limited perspective and pattern of rural grassroots cadres, making them susceptible to sectarianism. This is demonstrated in several ways. Firstly, the election of village committees lacks democracy, with village cadres often being members of the same family or small group with common interests. Additionally, villagers themselves may have a relatively weak sense of democracy, and vote-buying frequently occurs. Secondly, after the appointment of personnel, those who were elected and those who elected them often form a small circle, and personal connections and abuse of power for personal gain can lead to a loss of objectivity and impartiality in policy implementation, ultimately undermining the interests of villagers. Thirdly, grassroots cadres tend to have close ties with villagers or families with substantial financial resources, leading to a monopoly of interests and the spread of corruption. These "cliques" are catalysts for corruption and must be effectively eliminated.

Concentration of power and separation from the masses. At present, the implementation of the principle of democratic centralism in China's rural areas has been inadequate, resulting in significant problems in the power operation mechanism. Many village committees exist only in name, giving rise to a situation where the village secretary wields ultimate authority in all major and minor affairs of the village, leading to a "one person, one voice" phenomenon. Other team members and villagers have no say in decision-making. As the top leader of the grassroots party organization, the village secretary enjoys excessive freedom and power in handling various affairs. This not only deviates from democratic principles and infringes on the interests of the masses, but also leads to corrupt practices such as lazy administration, abuse of power, trading of power, and intensification of social contradictions.

Characteristics of grassroots power corruption

Team corruption is outstanding. Corruption at the local level often involves a group of individuals who collude to embezzle state funds and exploit their positions for personal gain. The leader of the group works in tandem with their accomplices to withhold or misappropriate state funds and sell agricultural products for personal gain. The secretary of the village committee works together with the village chief or accountant to embezzle public funds. Moreover, there is team-based corruption in accepting bribes from external funds, which involves a leader and related businessmen. This is mainly because of the close relationships that develop during the process of land requisition, demolition, and transfer in the village. The party secretary and leaders of construction, demolition, or other commercial companies often receive or initiate bribes. In addition to embezzlement, there is a pattern of collusion between local officials and villagers. For instance, officials responsible for land requisition and demolition take

advantage of their positions and knowingly participate in fraudulent activities by relocated households, who intentionally decorate their properties to defraud the state of compensation. The officials also accept significant amounts of alcohol, tobacco, and gifts from relocated households and decorators to verify the fraudulent decoration and process the compensation. This not only causes a loss of state assets but also tarnishes the government's reputation at the local level.

Long time-span and strong concealment. Corruption among grassroots management personnel often persists for a prolonged period, ranging from three to eight years. This is due to the fact that most of the cadres at the grassroots level are local residents and have held their positions for a considerable time. They tend to view their villages as separate "kingdoms," thus hindering the exchange of information between the higher-level government and the villagers. As a result, most villagers are unaware of the policies of the higher-level government aimed at benefiting farmers. This provides an opportunity for some grassroots cadres to exploit loopholes for an extended time. Such illegal and disorderly behaviors include extortion, embezzlement, and sale of state materials allocated free of charge, often in collaboration with other cadres. Villagers are generally unaware of these activities, and thus some violations of discipline and laws remain unreported for many years. This highlights the hidden nature of corruption among grassroots cadres, making it difficult to detect. Additionally, grassroots power corruption includes both "obvious problems" such as dereliction of duty, improper work styles, and illegal land occupation, and "hidden problems" like corruption, bribery, and financial misconduct. The latter are more harmful, yet harder to investigate and address.

The time point of grassroots power corruption is typical. Illegal diversion or embezzlement of national project funds is most prevalent during the busy farming seasons when the grassroots workload is high and prone to errors. Furthermore, due to the concentration of fund allocation, the workload is heavy in the short term, creating opportunities for corrupt activities. The initial stage for bribery often begins during the early days of holidays or when traveling together. High time for grassroots cadres to receive bribes is often the day before the Dragon Boat Festival, Spring Festival, and other holidays. When grassroots cadres and businessmen travel together, bribers take advantage of the opportunity to offer bribes. Such bribery activities also extend to subsequent stages of investment promotion and project development. In villages and towns where there are opportunities for capital inflows, such as infrastructure construction and land transfer, corruption among grassroots cadres is frequent before and after bidding, especially during periods of frequent contacts between relevant personnel.

The root causes of power corruption of grassroots cadres

Weak legal awareness. Compared to central, provincial, municipal, and county-level cadres, weak discipline among some grassroots cadres is not only a major characteristic of contemporary grassroots party and government departments in China but also a significant cause of micro-corruption among them. Grassroots cadres are generally recruited based on their qualifications, prestige, clan power, and even their "black-related" background, and hence the threshold and standard for their selection are not high. They lack knowledge and cultural refinement, as well as familiarity with party discipline and national laws. Although the "Regulations on Honest Performance of Duties by Rural Grassroots Cadres" (for Trial Implementation) of the Chinese government explicitly states that rural grassroots cadres are not permitted to "extort, defraud or intercept, or divide privately the state's compensation for collective land, subsidies and various subsidies and project support funds by means of false reports and false claims," many grassroots cadres still engage in corrupt practices under the guise of precision

poverty alleviation. This highlights the importance of strengthening legal consciousness as a psychological foundation for ensuring the integrity of grassroots cadres.

Furthermore, the countryside is a relatively complete field for traditional cultural heritage, and the deep-rooted perspectives on power still hold sway. Some grassroots cadres have no legal awareness and were elected through bribery and bullying, which violates discipline. They view power as something won by themselves, not out of the trust of the organization or the people, and therefore believe it is "natural" to use it to seek benefits for themselves. These traditional views, which are incompatible with party discipline, often become the root of corruption. Under the influence of false consciousness, a small number of cadres at the grassroots level view various corrupt acts, such as "false information for receiving subsistence allowances," "defrauding orphans of basic living expenses," "defrauding subsidies for renovation of dilapidated buildings," or "withholding funds for returning farmland to forests" in accurate poverty alleviation as unimportant transgressions. Some cadres at the grassroots level think that "violating discipline is only a minor issue, and breaking the law is a big thing," completely disregarding party discipline and even "setting an example of discipline" for petty gain. These violations of discipline infringe on the vital interests of farmers. Some grassroots cadres, especially "top leaders," only use discipline as a tool to restrain their "subordinates" and "restrain others but not themselves." They believe that as long as higher-level departments do not supervise them, they will not be exposed even if they are corrupt. In the long run, they forget the party's discipline and the dignity of the law.

Excessive concentration of power. Power is a force used to adjust production and life, as well as to deal with public affairs, in order to meet the needs of people. Fundamentally, it is a relationship dominated by specific forces with the objective of realizing public interests. The subject of power can be divided into two parts: the owner of power, who is the masses of the people, and the exerciser of power, who is the leading cadre. The relationship between them should have been based on entrustment and delegation. The latter should use the power given by the former to serve the former. However, the division of the subject of power has become a condition that can induce corruption, as power is a scarce resource that can bring honor and status to those in power that ordinary people cannot enjoy, making it inherently corrosive and tempting. Although an appropriate concentration of power is necessary to ensure the smooth realization of authority and public interests, things can turn out differently when power is overly concentrated, which can lead to corruption. Over-concentration of power is a common problem in the vast grassroots areas of China, where the "top leaders" usually hold the reins. The excessive concentration of power in the hands of the "top leaders," who often control the allocation of all basic resources and personnel discretion, is an important reason for the corruption of grassroots cadres. It can be predicted that once unsupervised and over-centralized power encounters individual greed, corruption of all kinds will inevitably ensue.

Lack of effective supervision. The saying "absolute power leads to absolute corruption" holds true, as unsupervised power can be extremely dangerous. When power is not properly supervised, it exposes the evil and greedy side of those who wield it. Power can be distorted and used as a tool for individuals to seek their own interests at the expense of others. This is why lack of supervision is the most significant reason for corruption among grassroots managers. Research has shown that varying degrees of lack of supervision is a common factor in the corruption of grassroots cadres.

The lack of supervision among grassroots cadres is a major reason for corruption. Grassroots cadres usually commit corruption acts that directly harm the vital interests of the grassroots masses. This is why the grassroots masses often have the strongest reactions to corruption and despise it the most. Effective supervision of grassroots cadres by the grassroots themselves would be an ideal way

to control corruption. However, due to various reasons, this form of supervision is not always realized. Some grassroots cadres engage in covert operations, resulting in asymmetric information between them and the masses they serve. Government affairs and work may not be carried out in accordance with procedures, and the masses may be "kept in the dark" without any means of supervision.

Another reason for the corruption of grassroots cadres is the lack of supervision by functional departments at the same level. In the grassroots political power structure, it is not uncommon for grassroots cadres to act both as a player and as a referee. In rural areas, some "top leaders" hold decision-making, executive, and supervisory power, becoming paternalistic leaders without proper supervision by functional departments at the same level. Cronyism and meticulous attention to personal relationships have led to grassroots cadres controlling resources, appointing and removing personnel, and subordinates becoming afraid of displeasing their leaders. This form of horizontal supervision has become mere formalism.

Finally, lack of superior supervision can also lead to corruption among rural grassroots cadres. Vertical supervision, which comes from the top down, should be the most effective form of supervision. However, it is often absent in the countryside. In precision poverty alleviation, almost all cases of corruption among rural grassroots cadres result from the lack of superior supervision. Inadequate supervision has led to widespread corruption that has significantly harmed the vital interests of farmers.

Outcomes from corruption of power at the grassroots level

According to the theory that "all human pursuits are related to their interests," political relations and activities are motivated by interests. Interests refer to "the necessity of acquiring social content and characteristics based on a certain production basis." The public interest is the objective requirement for survival and development, which relies on one's intelligence and subjective initiative. Corruption at the grassroots level brings endless harm and mainly impacts the following areas.

Infringing on the vital interests of the regular people. The corruption of a few rural cadres at the grassroots level directly infringes on the self-interest of the poor peasants. Compared with huge corruption, which is often millions, tens or even hundreds of millions of dollars, corruption at the grassroots level often involves a small amount of corruption. However, this kind of corruption brings great harm to the grassroots level, such as food subsidies for agriculture, funds for reservoir resettlement, funds for renovation of dilapidated buildings, agricultural subsidies, winter and spring aid, returning farmland to forests, land resettlement, etc. These are often areas where corruption among cadres at the grassroots level in rural areas is prone to occur and occurs frequently. Some rural grassroots cadres abuse their power to engage in covert operations on poverty alleviation funds and projects to seek personal gain for themselves or others, which will inevitably infringe upon the vital interests of those farmers who urgently need precise poverty alleviation. What's more, the corruption of grassroots cadres has dealt a heavy blow to the "precision poverty alleviation" families, because there are many projects involved in precision poverty alleviation, such as post-disaster reconstruction grants and the basic living expenses of families with five guarantees, families with low-income families, orphans and children with no one to support. For them, the poverty-stricken farmers in urgent need of assistance, the poverty alleviation funds have absolute significance. Money taken by corrupt grassroots cadres are undoubtedly the "survival money" and "life-saving money" that many people depend on. Therefore, the corruption of grassroots power will undoubtedly cause great damage to the interests of the grassroots.

Depriving people's sense of achievement. The sense of achievement denotes the satisfaction one feels upon obtaining certain benefits. In recent years, it has gained popularity in China's society as a "hot word on the internet" and a "high-frequency word." Based on the fundamental principles of political science, the sense of achievement emerges as a spontaneous psychological activity resulting from a political subject's performance of political behavior within a political organization. It is directly connected to the political subject's political cognition, emotion, and evaluation of the political organization (Sleat, 2016). The central government has implemented the "precision poverty alleviation" livelihood projects to expedite the exit of poor farmers from poverty. Numerous poverty alleviation materials and projects are aimed at poor rural areas, which could have provided poor farmers with a stronger sense of access. Nevertheless, a small number of grassroots cadres, mainly those who manage the poverty alleviation materials, abuse their power, withhold personal gains, make false claims, or cheat and embezzle to reap benefits for themselves or their kin. Consequently, poverty-stricken farmers who genuinely require the materials are unable to access them. The repercussions not only impinge on the justice and equity of rural communities, but also erode the poor farmers' sense of acquisition. All that the poor farmers experience is a bleak sense of deprivation, which can lead to negative or even adverse political cognition, emotion, and evaluation of the Party. Since the corruption of grassroots cadres infringes on their vital interests, their sense of achievement is bound to disappear.

The sense of achievement for people at the grassroots level is derived from the tangible benefits they receive. Therefore, farmers' sense of achievement should stem from sharing the fruits of reform and development, improving their livelihoods, and enhancing the performance of governance by tackling corruption among grassroots cadres. Only by addressing the issue of corruption among grassroots cadres, which has a significant impact on the lives of peasants, and by allowing them to continuously realize and enjoy the benefits of a fully and strictly governed Party, can the "anti-corruption struggle bring more sense of achievement to the common people." Therefore, the central government must prioritize the problem of micro-corruption among grassroots cadres and take effective measures to continuously raise awareness about anti-corruption among the people.

Initiating a crisis of trust in the government. When a government loses credibility, regardless of its actions or words, the society will give it a negative evaluation leading to the Tacitus trap. This term refers to the crisis of trust in political organizations by their subjects. The legitimacy of political parties and government organizations in power stems from the universal trust and rational identification of political subjects. If political subjects lose their trust in political organizations, there will be a legitimacy crisis, which could even endanger the ruling foundation of political organizations, as noted by Habermas (1988). The authority and credibility of the government form the basis of power legitimacy and the premise of the passage of government decrees. If the government fails to maintain credibility effectively, China's politics may fall into the Tacitus trap.

The corruption of grassroots cadres may trigger a crisis of trust in the party among poor farmers. Grassroots cadres have the most contact with the bottom population, and their actions have the most direct impact. Moreover, since grassroots cadres are also government cadres, their words and deeds inevitably affect the government's image. The corruption of a few grassroots cadres can damage the vital interests of poor farmers and erode their sense of gain. Such damage to the party's positive image in the eyes of poor farmers can cause a crisis of confidence in the party and the country.

Generating uneven distribution of resources. Resource allocation is one of the main mechanisms that contribute to rural income inequality. Corrupt officials often prioritize the interests of their social network over those of society, thereby distributing resources such as land, loans, and business licenses to individuals who offer bribes or favors to local officials. As a result, a few elites

amass wealth and resources, while the majority remains impoverished. Corruption at the grassroots level exacerbates the unequal distribution of resources. For instance, in many rural areas, land ownership determines an individual's wealth and social status. Corrupt officials allocate land to those who are already wealthy and influential, perpetuating long-term income inequalities between urban and rural areas.

In addition, the distribution of resources through corrupt means can lead to the concentration of wealth in specific industries or sectors. Corrupt officials may give priority to their acquaintances in the logging or mining industries by granting loans and business licenses to them, resulting in wealth being concentrated in those industries. This unequal distribution of resources may lead to some industries being dominated by a few elites while others remain underdeveloped.

Recommendations to reduce the corruption of grassroots cadres

Strengthen the discipline awareness of grassroots cadres. To reinforce discipline awareness among grassroots cadres, the primary focus should be on carrying out education. A variety of learning activities should be conducted at the grassroots level, such as attending classes, irregular training, and regular learning. Through these activities, grassroots cadres can study the relevant laws and regulations, can understand what is permitted and what is not, and can create a rule-following pattern of behavior. Additionally, grassroots cadres should be regularly reminded of the importance of discipline through various educational activities, including increasing legal education and holding itinerant lectures on discipline inspection and supervision.

It is necessary to establish and improve the system and mechanism for the rotation of cadres at the grassroots level, and strictly require their participation in training as part of the cadre assessment indicators. This will serve as an important basis for selection, re-election, promotion, and advancement, and it will encourage grassroots cadres to consciously follow discipline and regulations. To achieve this, we can draw from the experience of other countries and regions known for their integrity in training and educating grassroots management cadres, and tailor the approach to the specific realities of grassroots work in China. Through these efforts, we can create a practical and feasible education and training model for grassroots cadres. In addition, the important role of upper party and government organs as a base for training grassroots cadres should be fully utilized. However, the current weakness of party schools at the county and township levels has become a bottleneck that restricts the political education of grassroots cadres.

Improve the management system of grassroots cadres. The reason why grassroots level cadres are prone to corruption is closely related to the imperfect management system of these cadres and their inadequate implementation. Firstly, in the long-term practice of grassroots management, many effective management systems for grassroots cadres have been worked out by the party and the state, including the grassroots administrative examination and approval system, grassroots financial management system, grassroots government affairs openness system, grassroots post responsibility system, and grassroots cadres' accountability system. Most of the corruption of grassroots cadres is related to the loopholes in some systems or their inadequately implemented aspects. Secondly, some grassroots level cadres, especially the "top leaders," have exploited the loopholes in the grassroots financial management system by using their relatives, who do not know finance and accounting at all, to provide convenience for themselves. To address this issue, the meritocracy system, the government affairs openness system, and the accountability mechanism must be coordinated.

Strengthen the discipline supervision of grassroots cadres. The power of grassroots cadres is not subject to supervision, which inevitably leads to corruption. Therefore, to control corruption

among grassroots cadres, disciplinary supervision must be strengthened and implemented. Firstly, we should strengthen discipline supervision over grassroots cadres by the grassroots. Given the current plight of grassroots people, who are unwilling, afraid, and unable to supervise, the party and the state should improve and perfect the rights protection system, petition system, and real-name reporting exemption system. This will provide grassroots people with more unimpeded and worry-free supervision channels. Moreover, discipline inspection departments at higher levels should respond, follow up, investigate, and deal with the reports made by the grassroots, thereby giving full play to the enthusiasm and initiative of the grassroots as the main body of supervision. Grassroots cadres who retaliate against informants should be severely punished. Secondly, we will strengthen the discipline supervision of grassroots cadres by functional departments at the same level, especially discipline inspection departments. To solve the problem of over-centralization of power at the grassroots level without supervision, power must be allocated scientifically and rationally. This can be achieved through power decomposition, scientific allocation, and regular rotation of posts. To effectively implement the main responsibility and supervision responsibility, the right must be accompanied by responsibility, and the right to use must be subject to supervision. Party organizations at all levels at the grassroots level should assume the responsibility of leading the main body, while discipline inspection departments at all levels at the grassroots level should assume the responsibility of supervision. This will form a mechanism where decision-making, execution, and supervision powers restrict each other.

Strengthen the inspection of higher-level functional departments. Superior supervision is more effective and deterrent. The key to strengthening supervision by higher authorities is to prioritize the practical implementation of supervision, instead of focusing on form over content and engaging in perfunctory work. Efforts should be made to take supervision seriously and ensure effective discipline supervision to the very end. Local discipline inspection departments at all levels should follow the central government's example in conducting inspections at the grassroots level. They should be adept at identifying key areas and issues during inspections. To make people-benefiting projects truly effective, we should pay close attention to and make good use of the poverty alleviation funds, subsistence allowances, medical insurance funds, and other resources that are essential for the survival and well-being of the masses.

To sum up, although there are many differences between the corruption of grassroots cadres and the massive corruption of senior leaders, their essence is the same and their consequences should not be underestimated. It is related to people's livelihoods and their well-being, and it is directly linked to the ruling foundation of the Party and the people's happiness. The corruption of grassroots cadres has far-reaching implications and its reduction should be a goal of the entire society. The ultimate goal of combating corruption among grassroots cadres is not only to punish corrupt individuals but also to put the spirit of the legal system into practice and to safeguard the vital interests of the grassroots to the greatest extent possible.

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